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Power, Politics, and Public Health: Understanding the Role of Healthcare Expenditure in Shaping Health Outcomes in Pakistan for Policy Enhancement

Sitara Saleem¹

ABSTRACT

Power dynamics and political structures play a significant role in determining resource allocation, policy decisions, and health outcomes in public health. The main purpose of this research is to analyze the impact of healthcare spending on health outcomes in Pakistan between 2002 and 2021. Government spending on education, existing health expenses, carbon emissions, illness prevalence (both infectious and non-infectious), and the availability of doctors are only a few of the issues investigated. The health outcomes are measured by the percentage of infants who die before their fifth birthday. The robust least squares regression technique is used to test the hypotheses. The results show that the under-5 death rate in Pakistan has increased due to a lack of government spending on education, current health expenses, and infectious illnesses. However, it has been demonstrated that increasing the number of doctors may help reduce health-damaging effects, especially the death rate for children under five. Based on these results, several policy recommendations can be made. Firstly, the government should allocate more funds to healthcare in regions where access to healthcare facilities is inadequate. Secondly, there is a need to upgrade outdated health infrastructure by incorporating the latest advancements in healthcare technologies, with the aim of improving the overall healthcare system in the country. Lastly, promoting a healthier lifestyle and a cleaner environment is crucial for enhancing longevity. To achieve this, it is imperative to adopt renewable energy technologies to reduce pollution levels. This study serves as a reminder that public health is intricately intertwined with power dynamics and political contexts. By critically examining these relationships and embracing a health-in-all-policies approach, we can create transformative change that prioritizes the health and well-being of populations, ultimately leading to a more just and equitable society.

Keywords: Health politics; Health expenditures; Health outcomes; Communicable diseases; Carbon emissions; Health infrastructure; Pakistan.

1. INTRODUCTION

Healthcare spending plays a vital role in the provision of health services and can have a positive impact on human capital and overall productivity, thus contributing to economic performance. Evaluating healthcare spending in a country is important due to its potential influence on health outcomes, such as life expectancy, mortality rates, and overall well-being (Fatima, 2023). However, research results have been contradictory regarding the correlation between healthcare expenditures and patient outcomes (Ullah et al., 2021).

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Government expenditure, mandatory health insurance, optional health insurance, and private funding, including out-of-pocket payments by families, NGOs, and private enterprises, all contribute to healthcare finance (OECD, 2023) differently. How much money a nation should allocate to healthcare depends on its unique problems. Savedoff (2007) notes that countries with low rates of infectious illness but high rates of cancer and chronic diseases may demand different healthcare expenditure levels than those with impoverished populations and a high prevalence of malaria and HIV/AIDS. Evidence-based and international comparisons inform the goal of dedicating at least 5% of GDP to health expenditure by governments. Before the COVID-19 pandemic hit in 2019, healthcare spending in OECD nations averaged 8.8% of GDP, which has remained constant since 2013. The United States spent 16.8% of its GDP on healthcare, more than double the 11.7 percent spent by Germany. Additionally, several high-income countries, including France, Canada, Japan, and the United Kingdom, allocated more than 10% of their GDP to healthcare. Other countries, such as Brazil and South Africa, along with some central and eastern European OECD countries, spent between 8% and 10% of their GDP on healthcare. Mexico, Turkey, China, and India allocated less than 6% of their GDP to healthcare. There is a clear link between healthcare spending and increased life expectancy. Life expectancy serves as a key indicator of overall population health. Countries that allocate higher per capita spending to healthcare generally exhibit higher life expectancy rates (Aqib & Zaman, 2023). However, the relationship between total healthcare expenditure and life expectancy depends on the equitable distribution of financial resources. The United States is the top global spender on healthcare as a percentage of GDP, yet its life expectancy is significantly lower than the OECD average. Various factors contribute to this discrepancy, including affordability, access, and equality issues between different socioeconomic groups (Acheampong et al., 2023). Administrative costs in the US are also considerably higher compared to other countries, resulting in increased burdens on healthcare professionals. For instance, nurses in the US spend 18 more hours per week on administrative tasks compared to their Canadian counterparts, and clerical staff work an additional 37 hours (World Economic Forum, 2023). While individuals in the wealthiest parts of the world are experiencing longer life expectancies, access to basic healthcare remains a challenge in many other regions. Universal health coverage in most affluent countries provides financial protection against illness-related costs (Khan & Imran, 2023). However, the relationship between significant healthcare spending and higher life expectancy depends on the equitable distribution of financial resources.

In addition to healthcare expenditure, positive socioeconomic conditions and healthy lifestyles also contribute to increased life expectancy. Education and gender are significant indicators of life expectancy, with individuals having a tertiary education tending to live longer than those with lower levels of education. The largest disparity in life expectancy is observed between tertiary-educated men and their less-educated counterparts. Global health expenditure in 2015 reached 7.3 trillion USD, accounting for approximately 10% of global GDP. Between 2000 and 2015, health expenditure grew at an annual rate of 4%, surpassing the economic growth rate of 2.8%. However, healthcare spending remains highly unequal worldwide, with over 80% of the global population residing in low and middle-income countries, but accounting for only 20% of healthcare expenditure. Half of the world's nations spend less than \$366 per person on healthcare, even though the worldwide average is \$1,011. Worldwide, 2.7 billion people in over 50 countries in 2015 had a health budget of less than \$100 (WHO, 2017). Since China's economic reforms in 1978, healthcare spending has increased by 12.5% per year, outpacing the country's economic growth rate of 9.9% from 1993 to 2012 (Zhai et al., 2015). Health spending as a whole, and public health spending in particular, has been linked to longer lifespans and lower rates of infant mortality in the Southeast Asian area between the years 2000 and 2014. Increases in public health spending, as measured by the universal health coverage index, are positively correlated with expansions in healthcare access by a factor of 0.26 for every one percentage point in the expenditure total. Behera and Dash (2020) found that educating girls significantly improved food security and vaccination rates. Increases in healthcare spending are associated with better health outcomes, including longer life expectancy and lower death and infant mortality rates, notably in sub-Saharan African nations (Novignon et al., 2012). There is a favorable correlation between health status and public and private healthcare expenditure, with public health spending having a significantly bigger influence. This highlights the importance of carefully investing in various aspects of healthcare to enhance income, GDP, productivity, and poverty alleviation (Tanweer et al., 2023; Zaman, 2023a). Given these potential benefits, further research is warranted to explore universal access to healthcare.

Increased expenditure per case of disease or injury is evaluated against the increase in disability-adjusted life-years (DALYs) saved per case to determine the efficacy of healthcare spending (Weaver et al., 2022). Indicators of healthcare expenditure are crucial for keeping an eye on budgets, helping shape healthcare policy, and fostering a culture of openness and responsibility. As a result of the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020, there were widespread adjustments to healthcare systems throughout the globe. Global health expenditure reached a record high of almost USD 9 trillion (equal to 11% of global GDP) due to a dramatic rise in healthcare spending by governments across all socioeconomic levels. Government health expenditure increased to meet different pandemic-related preventive, detection, and treatment requirements, offsetting the decreases in individual spending. Increasing social protection expenditure in high- and upper-middle-income nations was also a component of the budgetary reaction to the pandemic aimed at reducing the economic effects of COVID-19. Amid worsening macroeconomic circumstances and mounting debt payments, maintaining increased public expenditure on health and other social sectors is difficult (Sadiqa, 2023). In addition, reducing poverty, expanding access to healthcare, and bolstering pandemic preparation all depend on low-income nations receiving consistent funding from outside. Government health expenditure is affected by allocations for other social purposes like education and welfare. Health and social protection get a bigger percentage of public expenditure in higher-income nations. In contrast, education receives a smaller part (Khan, 2023) due to the demographic shift brought on by an increasing working-age population. However, purchasing habits vary widely from one nation to the next. In 2020, healthcare costs amounted to about 10% of global GDP, or \$9 trillion. There was a large disparity in expenditure across different income brackets. All income brackets saw increases in government health expenditure, although the biggest percentage increase (18.6%) was seen in low-income nations. Depending on household income, the increases went mostly toward preventative care, health system administration and management, and diagnostic and therapeutic procedures. Over

60% of overall health expenditure in 2019 in 109 countries with available data was dedicated to inpatient and outpatient treatment and medical commodities, while the other 40% was spent on preventative care, health system governance and administration, and other health services.

As a middle-to-low-income nation, Pakistan's healthcare system is plagued by inadequate resources and trained personnel, poor coverage, and high costs. High rates of both maternal and newborn mortality, as well as rapid population increase, characterize the country's health profile (Zaman, 2023b). Curative healthcare is prioritized above preventative, environmental, social, and cultural ones, and just 3.4% of Pakistan's budget is set aside for healthcare facilities. There often must be more time between creating healthcare policy and its implementation. When adopting policies from affluent countries, developing nations like Pakistan often need to pay more attention to their inadequate healthcare infrastructure (Nazir, 2023). Healthcare in Pakistan is difficult because of the high expense of private treatment. While government workers and members of the military forces have access to free healthcare at public hospitals, only around a quarter of the population uses them. Higher life expectancy and the ability to spend heavily on health and its determinants, particularly greater access to healthcare, are hallmarks of economically developed nations. Interventions in fields as diverse as education, community development, policy, law, and regulation all contribute to a larger goal of improving people's health. Non-communicable illnesses, communicable diseases, injuries, and violence are all targets of these programs. Pakistan's government has launched several initiatives to improve the health of its citizens, notably that of its women and children. The Lady Health Worker Programme (LHWP) is one such program that was established in 1994. The program's major goal is to improve national health indices by reducing poverty by providing the population with needed primary healthcare services. In addition to its primary focus on improving the health of mothers and children, the program also offers family planning services and seeks to integrate other vertical health promotion initiatives.

The following are the research questions emerged with the stated discussions, which need to answer in this study. i.e.,

1. What is the impact of government investment in education on health outcomes in Pakistan from 2002 to 2021?
2. How does current health expenditure influence the under-5 mortality rate in Pakistan?
3. What is the relationship between the number of physicians and health outcomes, specifically the under-5 mortality rate, in Pakistan?

Based on the given research inquiry, the study has the following research objectives, i.e.,

1. To assess the influence of government investment in education on health outcomes, particularly the under-5 mortality rate, in Pakistan from 2002 to 2021.
2. To examine the relationship between current health expenditure and the under-5 mortality rate in Pakistan.
3. To investigate the impact of the number of physicians on health outcomes, specifically the under-5 mortality rate, in Pakistan.

The stated objectives will be assessed using advanced statistical methods to develop sustainable healthcare policies for the economy of Pakistan.

2. Literature Review

Spending on healthcare directly affects the accessibility and cost of essential healthcare components, including hospitals, doctors, pharmaceuticals, and new medical equipment. Allocating healthcare funds is essential for improving population health and lowering health inequalities such as mortality and illness rates. When people are healthier, they are more inclined to work and contribute to society's progress; therefore, spending money on healthcare multiplies economic growth and productivity. Hassan et al. (2013) examined how healthcare spending, GDP growth, and health outcomes were connected in SAARC countries. The research showed that healthcare costs, GDP growth, and health outcomes were interconnected over the long term. Life expectancy and the percentage of the population that is 65 and older both seemed to increase when healthcare costs went up. Sirag et al. (2017) conducted research in Sub-Saharan African nations that looked at the connection between health funding, CO₂ emissions, and health outcomes. Increased public health funding was proven to have a beneficial effect on population health. Further investigation on the link between CO₂ emissions and health effects is warranted. The research also highlighted the significance of socioeconomic variables as important predictors of health outcomes, including income and education. A new analysis of the correlation between government involvement in the health sector and health outcomes in Ghana was published in 2018 by Kofi et al. The research concluded that public health spending and income were critical in enhancing health outcomes in Ghana. The results bolstered the case for additional investment in the health sector by highlighting the beneficial relationship between government health expenditure and better health outcomes. Environmentally raised levels of carbon dioxide (CO₂) below 5,000 parts per million (ppm) were argued by Jacobson et al. (2019) to represent direct dangers to human health. They looked at the dangers of long-term exposure to CO₂ concentrations in the natural world. Some potential adverse effects are inflammation, cognitive decline, bone demineralization, renal calcification, oxidative stress, and endothelial dysfunction. Researchers noted potential danger at concentrations as low as 1,000 ppm. A major stressor with possible health effects is prolonged exposure to increased ambient CO₂ levels, which are already exceeded in many indoor situations. To fully evaluate the health implications of breathing greater levels of CO₂ inside and to identify the sources of CO₂ exposure, further study is required. The relationship between education and mother and child health in low and medium-income countries was evaluated by Mensch et al. (2019). Newborn, baby, child mortality, stunting, and wasting were examined as child health indicators. The results showed that schooling positively impacted baby and child health, even in models that did not consider endogeneity. When endogeneity was taken into account, however, the impacts diminished. This research's findings highlight the need to account for endogeneity when evaluating the connection between maternal and child health and educational attainment. The inequalities in

newborn death rates by age and cause in the United States by race/ethnicity, socioeconomic status, and geographic location were studied by Singh & Yu (2019). The research indicated that overall newborn mortality rates and those for black and white babies had decreased significantly. However, racial differences in mortality grew until 2000, with the gaps being most prominent in post-neonatal death. The study's findings underscore the need for focused efforts to reduce socioeconomic gaps in newborn mortality and boost overall infant health outcomes. Under-five mortality (U5M) in sub-Saharan nations was studied by Van Malderen et al. (2019), who determined the proportional contribution of socioeconomic determinants to U5M variation. The research found that the mother's education, sex, family income, and location were the key drivers of U5M variation among nations. The results highlighted the need for measures that cut across sectors to boost child survival rates. Shaw Taylor (2020) gave a historical context for infectious illnesses, epidemics, and longevity gains, primarily in England. Life expectancy in the world has increased dramatically from around 30 years in 1800 to over 73 years in 2019. There was talk of how we have come so far in the fight against things like starvation and the plague and how we have come so far in the fight against things like smallpox, malaria, and typhus. The article highlighted important achievements in the fight against infectious illnesses and underlined the impact of socioeconomic variables in increasing life expectancy. Overall, it was an upbeat account of how medical science has come a long way and how human life spans have grown. Raghupathi & Raghupathi (2020) examined the link between schooling and health nationwide, with policy and management repercussions. Twenty-six OECD nations' data from the OECD and the World Bank were analyzed visually. The time covered 1995-2015. The research showed that people with greater levels of education are healthier and live longer than those with lower levels of education. Crucial health indices, including newborn mortality, life expectancy, child immunization rates, and enrollment rates, were shown to be affected by higher education. The research concluded a strong correlation between educational attainment and health on a national scale, with the former having the capacity to ameliorate health outcomes, lessen health disparities, and direct policy choices toward more efficient health administration.

By investigating the possible moderating impact of non-renewable energy use in the connection between carbon emissions, environmental deterioration, and death rates, Barua et al. (2022) provide a valuable contribution to the health-environment literature. Data from 42 Asian and Pacific nations were used in their study. The negative effect of environmental deterioration on health was highlighted by the study's finding that carbon emissions led to increased death rates. Furthermore, it was shown that using non-renewable energy sources reduces mortality, indicating possible health advantages linked with this energy source. These results shed light on the intricate web connecting the use of fossil fuels, environmental deterioration, and human mortality. Mahalik et al. (2022) studied carbon emissions and life expectancy in 68 poor and medium-income countries between 1990 and 2017. They looked at two factors: the consumption and production patterns contributing to nations' CO₂ emissions and the countries' respective stages of economic growth (developing and emerging). Life expectancy was lower in countries with higher CO₂ emissions, both overall and within the group of developing nations studied. This suggests that in these economies, greater CO₂ emissions are associated with reduced life expectancy, independent of the source of the emissions (consumption or production). The results underline the need for holistic policies that consider CO₂ emissions from both consumption and production to lower dangerous pollutants and improve public health. Using information collected from households across Pakistan, Asif et al. (2022) investigated the factors contributing to high infant and child mortality rates. The researchers used multivariate logistic regression to examine data from the 2017-18 Pakistan Demographic and Health Survey. The research indicated that child mortality was affected by characteristics such as mothers' levels of education and empowerment, fathers' levels of education, family income, the availability of plumbing and sewage systems, mothers' and fathers' exposure to the media, and the prevalence of unmet needs related to family planning. The research also found that the mother's level of education impacted infant mortality but that the wealth index of the family acted as a moderator. The results underline the necessity for targeted interventions in lower-income families and the significance of socioeconomic determinants in lowering child mortality. The infant mortality rate (IMR) in France was analyzed by Nhung et al. (2022) from 2001 through 2019. In this work, we used joint point regressions to locate IMR trend inflection points and evaluate their significance. The study found that IMR dropped rapidly from 2001 to 2005 and dropped more slowly from 2005 to 2012. However, there was a sharp rise in IMR starting in 2012. Subgroups were also analyzed depending on death age and gender. The results add to the work being done in France to improve the health of infants and lower infant mortality. From 2000 to 2018, researchers Bunyaminu et al. (2022) analyzed the correlation between total health spending and life expectancy in 43 African nations. Using the dynamic panel GMM estimation approach, the researchers discovered that healthcare spending increases longevity. However, this beneficial effect was mitigated by the moderating influence of government efficiency. The research results also highlighted the roles of education and employment in determining longevity. The results emphasize the need to invest in health care in Africa to increase life expectancy. Djoumessi (2022) analyzed data from 36 African nations between 2003 and 2018 to determine the effects of hunger on newborn mortality and life expectancy. The research indicated that newborn mortality decreased when malnutrition was light or moderate but increased when it was severe in children less than five years old. The research also examined how malnutrition impacts the economy by perpetuating cycles of poverty, poor diet, low productivity, and food insecurity. According to the results, malnutrition must be addressed economically and medically. Azzouzi et al. (2022) studied NCD patients' healthy practices and mental and physical health evaluations during the COVID-19 pandemic. NCD patients are sicker than before the epidemic. Non-communicable illnesses did not significantly lower mental health. Non-communicable illnesses were also linked to higher body mass index and lower smoking rates. The data demonstrate how the epidemic has affected NCD patients. To this end, El-Shal et al. (2022) analyzed data from 111 countries between 2000 and 2019 to evaluate the impact of health crises on maternal and child mortality. The research underscores the significance of emergency preparation, health system capability, and socioeconomic determinants of health in reducing the impact of health catastrophes on mother and child mortality. The results have implications for policymakers and stakeholders in enhancing disaster response methods and strengthening health systems to safeguard vulnerable populations. In 508 districts or cities throughout Indonesia, Sunarya & POLITICA, 2(1), 58-72 (2023)

Djamaluddin (2023) studied the effect of regional income & spending budget on public health indicators. Data spanning 2014–2018 were included in their study, allowing for a holistic comprehension of all relevant independent factors. Local government investment in healthcare was shown to affect the quality of healthcare provided within an area favorably. Therefore, increasing the government's spending on healthcare improves public health. The study also found regional differences in Indonesia, with some islands having better than average health and others having worse than average health. These results highlight the need for targeted interventions and legislative actions to overcome resource inequities. In order to effectively handle complicated health concerns, it is crucial, as Laprise (2023) notes, to forge strong linkages among the many players involved—everyone from students to doctors to community members to people. A higher standard of living is possible when people are encouraged to work together and participate. Aging populations, globalization, and climate change are just a few elements the author uses to argue for a radically different approach to healthcare. One Health and sustainable health give navigational frameworks for these difficulties, allowing us to better people's lives while protecting the planet's health. Life expectancy in Pakistan was studied by Azam et al. (2023), who zeroed in on carbon emissions as a proxy for environmental deterioration. From 1975 through 2020, they analyzed data. The research demonstrated that CO₂ emissions, inflation rate, food production index, and mortality rate all negatively affect life expectancy. Conversely, life expectancy increases with higher levels of wealth, urbanization, population growth, birth rate, health spending, and education. The research emphasizes the role of affluence, urbanization, population growth, healthcare spending, and education in increasing life expectancy in Pakistan and recommends legislative steps to decrease carbon emissions.

The study's three research hypotheses were derived from the literature as mentioned above and are as follows:

H1: Public spending on education significantly affects health outcomes, especially the under-5 mortality rate in Pakistan.

H2: Current health expenditure significantly affects the under-5 mortality rate in Pakistan; and

H3: The number of physicians significantly affects health outcomes, especially the under-5 mortality rate in Pakistan.

This research significantly advances healthcare by analyzing the connection between healthcare costs and patient outcomes in Pakistan. The study provides insight into the relationship between the under-5 mortality rate and several factors, such as government spending on education, current health expenditures, carbon emissions, the prevalence of communicable and non-communicable diseases, and the number of physicians. The results are more rigorous and trustworthy because of strong statistical methods. This research contributes by conducting the first empirical investigation of the connection between healthcare spending and health outcomes in Pakistan. The study is helpful for policymakers, healthcare providers, and academics because it sheds light on the variables that affect health outcomes. Evidence-based insights on the significance of healthcare spending and its implications for health outcomes in Pakistan are provided, adding to the body of knowledge. In addition, the paper contributes by suggesting potential directions for future policymaking. The results stress the need to direct resources toward places that lack adequate healthcare infrastructure. The research highlights the need for Pakistan to improve its healthcare system overall by investing in health infrastructure upgrades and using cutting-edge technology. The research also emphasizes the importance of fostering a healthy lifestyle and a cleaner environment to better health outcomes and minimize health risks. The overall value of this research derives from the depth with which it examines the relationship between healthcare spending and health outcomes in Pakistan. The research hopes to aid in creating effective and sustainable healthcare policies that may lead to better health outcomes and greater well-being in the nation by producing new information and providing policy insights.

3. Materials and Methods

The list of variables and their respective measurements are shown in Table 1. The infant mortality rate (IMR) is the dependent variable. In contrast, current health expenditure (CHE), government expenditure on education (GEE), carbon emissions (CO₂), communicable disease (CD), non-communicable disease (NCD), and physician density (PHY) are the independent variables.

Table 1: List of Variables

Symbol	Variables description	Units of measurement
IMR	Infant mortality rate under-5	Per 1000 live births
GEE	Government expenditures on education	total (% of GDP)
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide emissions	Metric tons per capita
CHE	Current health expenditures	% of GDP
CD	Cause of death by communicable diseases and maternal, prenatal and nutrition conditions	% of total
NCD	cause of death, by non-communicable diseases	% of total
PHY	Number of physicians	Per 1000 people

Source: World Bank (2023).

The information utilized for the study spans 2002 through 2021 and was culled from the World Bank (2023). There has been much buzz in the academic community about the new cross-panel data approaches that have emerged recently. These methods illustrate the interconnectedness of national initiatives and reforms and the need to consider neighboring states' activities when developing sound policies (Zaman, 2023c). It has also become more common to use CiteScore Rank to index academic journals and manuscripts (Zaman, 2023d). Researchers used robust least squares (RLS) estimation to account for potentially outlying or important data points in the model. This approach, which includes M-estimator, S-estimator, and MM-estimator, is superior to ordinary least squares (OLS) estimation for dealing with outliers in such situations. Order statistics and various weighting techniques are used by robust approaches to identify anomalies and boost efficiency. The regression equation (1) represents the relationship between IMR and the independent variables.

$$\ln(IMR) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln(CHE) + \beta_2 \ln(GEE) + \beta_3 \ln(CO2) + \beta_4 \ln(CD) + \beta_5 \ln(NCD) + \beta_6 \ln(PHY) + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

Where, the coefficients β_1 , β_2 , β_3 , β_4 , β_5 , and β_6 correspond to CHE, GEE, CO2, CD, NCD, and PHY, respectively. The equation incorporates natural logarithms applied to all variables in the time series data to stabilize the relationship and mitigate any instability. The residual term ε represents the unexplained variation in the model.

4. Results and Discussion

Table 2 provides the descriptive statistics for the variables examined in the analysis. The average infant mortality rate (IMR) is approximately 4.403, indicating the typical value across the years studied. The range of IMR values spans from 4.14 to 4.55, with a relatively low standard deviation of 0.138, suggesting that the data points are closely clustered around the mean. The distribution of IMR is slightly skewed to the left (-0.452 skewness) and exhibits heavy tails (1.831 kurtosis), indicating some deviation from a normal distribution.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	IMR	GEE	CO2	CHE	CD	NCD	PHY
Mean	4.403205	0.858589	-0.253758	0.118815	3.637800	3.985083	-0.139391
Median	4.431326	0.888083	-0.230347	0.300159	3.656022	3.980044	-0.168576
Maximum	4.550186	1.099585	-0.127660	0.993275	3.833129	4.091939	0.012969
Minimum	4.148359	0.569617	-0.467201	-1.247866	3.500981	3.842872	-0.274437
Std. Dev.	0.137567	0.155746	0.104847	0.694003	0.102028	0.076747	0.105849
Skewness	-0.452298	-0.644944	-0.582232	-0.722109	0.160588	-0.171947	0.346898
Kurtosis	1.831204	2.602818	2.379405	2.384483	2.020252	2.042035	1.498788

Source: Author's estimate.

The variable representing government expenditure on education (GEE) has an average value of around 0.859, with values ranging from 0.57 to 1.099. The standard deviation is 0.1557, suggesting moderate variability in the data. The distribution of GEE is skewed to the left (-0.6449 skewness) and has a moderately heavy tail (2.60 kurtosis), indicating some departure from a symmetrical distribution. CO2 emissions (CO2) have an average value of approximately -0.254, with a range from -0.467 to -1.28. The standard deviation is 0.105, indicating relatively minimal variability in the data. The distribution of CO2 is slightly skewed to the left (-0.582 skewness) and has a moderately heavy tail (2.379 kurtosis), suggesting some deviations from a perfectly symmetric distribution. Current health expenditure (CHE) has an average value of about 0.1188, ranging from -1.248 to 0.993. The standard deviation is 0.694, indicating moderate variability in the data points. The distribution of CHE is slightly skewed to the left (-0.722 skewness) and has a moderately heavy tail (2.384 kurtosis), suggesting departures from a perfectly symmetrical distribution. Cause of death due to communicable diseases (CD) has a mean value of approximately 3.638, with values ranging from 3.501 to 3.833. The standard deviation is 0.102, indicating relatively minimal variation in the data. The distribution of CD is slightly skewed to the right (0.1605 skewness) and has a relatively heavy tail (2.02 kurtosis), suggesting some deviations from a perfectly symmetrical distribution. For cause of death due to non-communicable diseases (NCD), the mean value is about 3.985, ranging from 3.84 to 4.09. The standard deviation is 0.767, indicating moderate variability in the data points. The distribution of NCD is slightly skewed to the left (-0.172 skewness) and has a moderately heavy tail (2.042 kurtosis), suggesting some departures from a perfectly symmetrical distribution. The variable representing the number of physicians (PHY) has an average value of approximately -0.139, ranging from -0.274 to 0.012. The standard deviation is 0.106, indicating relatively minimal variation in the data. The distribution of PHY is slightly skewed to the right (0.347 skewness) and has a moderately heavy tail (1.499 kurtosis), suggesting some deviations from a perfectly symmetrical distribution.

Table 3 presents the correlation matrix, shedding light on the interrelationships among the variables: IMR, GEE, CO2, CHE, CD, NCD, and PHY. Understanding these correlations is crucial as they carry important economic implications.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix

Correlation Probability	IMR	GEE	CO2	CHE	CD	NCD	PHY
IMR	1.000000 ----						
GEE	-0.501181 0.0244	1.000000 ----					
CO2	-0.855940 0.0000	0.780878 0.0000	1.000000 ----				
CHE	0.987302 0.0000	-0.482298 0.0313	-0.880378 0.0000	1.000000 ----			
CD	0.948520 0.0000	-0.700270 0.0008	-0.951500 0.0000	0.941682 0.0000	1.000000 ----		
NCD	-0.949380 0.0000	0.890201 0.0008	0.948087 0.0000	-0.945453 0.0000	-0.993927 0.0000	1.000000 ----	
PHY	-0.979062 0.0000	0.473578 0.0349	0.814188 0.0000	-0.949400 0.0000	-0.914880 0.0000	0.911692 0.0000	1.000000 ----

Source: Author's estimate.

A very high positive association ($r = 0.987$) exists between "IMR" and both "CHE" and "CD" ($r = 0.949$). Infant mortality rates are predicted to rise in countries with higher healthcare costs and a higher incidence of infectious illnesses. These results show the need to invest strategically in healthcare and disease prevention to lower infant mortality and generally boost health outcomes. Conversely, "IMR" is inversely related to "NCD" ($r = -0.949$). This data implies that greater rates of NCDs are linked to decreased rates of infant mortality. This seems odd at first glance, but it may point to the fact that the mortality burden of non-communicable illnesses occurs later in life rather than in infancy. This link highlights the significance of tackling the growing epidemic of non-communicable illnesses on the health of a population over time. Strong negative correlations may also be shown between "IMR" and "PHY" ($r = -0.979$), "CO2" ($r = -0.856$), and "GEE" ($r = -0.501$). These associations show that lower infant death rates are linked to greater access to healthcare, fewer carbon dioxide emissions, and more public investment in education. These results highlight the significance of investments in healthcare infrastructure, environmental sustainability, and education in fostering healthy populations. When we look at the relationships between "GEE," "CO2," "NCD," and "PHY," we discover that they are all positively correlated with one another. This suggests that higher levels of public spending on education are associated with elevated levels of carbon emissions, non-communicable illnesses, and the availability of medical professionals. Because of these links, we need to consider how our educational policies affect people's health and strike a balance between funding education and protecting the environment. In addition to showing a strong association with "NCD" ($r = 0.946$), "CO2" also shows a positive correlation with "PHY" ($r = 0.814$), indicating that higher carbon emissions are linked to a higher incidence of non-communicable illnesses and a larger number of doctors. These results highlight the need for sustainable development plans that place a premium on environmental conservation and public health to mitigate the negative effects of carbon dioxide emissions on the environment and human health. For "CHE," we find a significant inverse link with NCD and PHY, suggesting that lower rates of non-communicable disease prevalence and fewer doctors are related to greater healthcare costs. The advantages of investing more in healthcare to fight non-communicable illnesses and maintain a sufficient healthcare workforce are highlighted. Finally, "CD" shows inverse associations with both NCD and PHY, suggesting that an increase in the frequency of communicable illnesses is linked to a decrease in the incidence of non-communicable diseases and the availability of medical professionals. These connections highlight the interconnected nature of illness and the need for healthcare systems that treat both communicable and non-communicable conditions simultaneously. Table 3 correlations show how different variables interact to produce health outcomes. They emphasize the need for evidence-based policies and initiatives to enhance population health and well-being by highlighting the financial consequences of healthcare spending, environmental sustainability, education, and illness prevalence.

Figure 1 show that test results deviate significantly from the norm. The R Student test finds one outlier or a value that deviates considerably from the norm. All data points, however, fall within the bounds predicted by the regression model, as shown by the Hat matrix test.

Influence Statistics

Figure 1: Influence Statistics

Source: Author's extract.

The DFFITS test, on the other hand, identifies one outlier. DFFITS is a measure of how influential a data point is on the overall regression model. This outlier is found to have a significant impact on the model's results. Additionally, the COVRATIO test identifies seven outliers. The COVRATIO is a measure of how well the regression model fits the data. These seven outliers indicate data points that substantially affect the model's fit, potentially influencing the estimated coefficients and overall interpretation of the regression analysis.

Figure 2 reveals the distribution of the model's regressors, or independent variables, around their respective average values. This distribution provides insight into the potential presence of outliers within the model. Outliers, if present, would manifest as data points that significantly deviate from the average values of the variables. Identifying outliers is crucial in regression analysis as they can exert undue influence on the estimated coefficients and affect the overall model fit. Outliers can arise due to various reasons, such as measurement errors, data entry mistakes, or extreme observations that are genuinely different from the majority of the data. By examining the distribution of the regressors in Figure 2, we can visually assess whether any data points fall far outside the expected range. If outliers are identified, it becomes necessary to carefully evaluate their impact on the regression results and consider appropriate actions, such as data cleaning or applying robust estimation techniques to mitigate their influence. The regression model results may be more confidently and accurately interpreted if the probability of outliers is considered.

The robust least squares regression analysis in Table 4 examines the association between the Infant Mortality Rate (IMR) and several economic factors specific to Pakistan. The estimated coefficients provide light on how various factors affect IMR. Government Expenditure on Education (GEE) positively correlates with IMR (with a coefficient of 0.228684) among the independent variables. This data indicates that increasing school spending may not automatically result in better health for babies. Several hypotheses may account for this finding. To begin, know there are many facets to the connection between schooling and health. Although education is typically thought to improve health and well-being, its effect on infant mortality may be affected by other variables (Eltayib et al., 2023) that are difficult to predict. The underlying causes of infant mortality, such as lack of access to healthcare, malnutrition, and poor sanitation, may need to be adequately addressed by GEE. Therefore, it's possible that a rise in GEE won't automatically result in better health for infants. Additionally, education's influence on health outcomes often acts via indirect routes, such as better maternal health, individual empowerment to make educated health-related choices, and promoting healthy behaviors (Farrell et al., 2023). These changes may take some time to become noticeable and may show up in the IMR after a while. Additionally, it is crucial to consider the quality and equity of education. Simply increasing the expenditure on education does not guarantee equitable access to quality education for all segments of the population. Disparities in educational opportunities and outcomes, particularly among marginalized communities, can perpetuate health inequalities and contribute to higher infant mortality rates (Curtis et al., 2023). From an economic perspective, this result suggests that policymakers need to carefully consider the allocation and effectiveness of education spending to ensure that it contributes to positive health outcomes. It highlights the importance of integrating health components into educational programs, improving healthcare infrastructure and accessibility, and addressing other social determinants of health alongside educational

initiatives. Addressing the underlying causes of infant mortality requires a comprehensive and coordinated approach that combines investments in education, healthcare, nutrition, sanitation, and other social determinants of health (Islam, 2023). Policymakers in Pakistan may improve the population's health as a whole and lower the IMR by focusing on these interconnected issues.

IMR vs. Variables (Partialled on Regressors)

Figure 2: Leverage Plots

Source: Author's extract.

CO2 emissions have a coefficient of 0.069, with a somewhat significant standard error of 0.075. At the 95% confidence level, there is no correlation between CO2 emissions and IMR in Pakistan since the coefficient is insignificant ($p = 0.359$). This finding emphasizes the need for more research into the intricate relationship between infants' environments and health. The coefficient of 0.063 for the relationship between current health expenditure (CHE) and IMR reveals a substantial positive influence. This suggests that a higher IMR is connected with a greater health expense. This data shows that increasing health expenditures may not improve baby health outcomes, which goes against common sense. Skjerve et al. (2023) note that this emphasizes the need to ensure efficient allocation and use of healthcare resources to meet identified public health concerns. This outcome might be due to several different things. Healthcare spending efficiency and effectiveness should be prioritized first. Spending more on healthcare may signify dedication to quality treatment, but the effect on health outcomes relies on how efficiently that money is spent (Whittington et al., 2023). More advances in

healthcare infrastructure, access to quality treatment, and health service delivery may result from efficient allocation or manipulation of finances, causing greater IMR (Kumar et al., 2023). Second, it is possible that inequities in the healthcare system and the positive correlation between CHE and IMR are to blame. It is possible for healthcare access gaps, particularly among low-income groups, to remain despite rising healthcare costs (Cobb, 2022). Health investment may not have an intended effect on lowering infant death rates due to inadequate coverage, restricted access to key healthcare services, and challenges reaching distant or marginalized communities (Budu et al., 2023). Additionally, other socioeconomic determinants of health, such as poverty, education, and sanitation, may impact the favorable correlation between CHE and IMR. The efficiency of health spending in boosting newborn health and lowering death rates may be stunted by insufficient investment in these areas, intimately connected to health outcomes. From a financial standpoint, this finding underlines the need to take a holistic approach to healthcare finance and provision. It highlights the need to improve healthcare systems generally, including infrastructure, access, and quality of treatment (Limna, 2023), and not only by boosting health spending. For improved health outcomes and lower infant mortality rates in Pakistan, targeted interventions are essential (Memon et al., 2023) that concentrate on enhancing healthcare access, lowering health inequities, and addressing socioeconomic determinants of health. For health spending to have the greatest impact on lowering infant mortality rates, policymakers should consider these consequences when formulating health policies and allocating resources. When Pakistan takes on the problems and disparities in its healthcare system, it may improve the health of its infants and its population (Ayan et al., 2023) in several ways.

Table 4: Robust Least Squares Regression Estimates

Dependent Variable: IMR				
Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-statistic	Probability
GEE	0.228684	0.067480	3.388915	0.0007
CO ₂	0.069161	0.07591	0.916146	0.3596
CHE	0.063680	0.014779	4.308720	0.0000
CD	1.432740	0.598211	2.395043	0.0166
NCD	-0.159470	0.250481	-0.636654	0.5243
PHY	-0.476238	0.065367	-7.285581	0.0000
C	3.520232	1.641306	2.144775	0.0320
R-Squared = 0.767; J.B Test: 0.290 (0.864); LM test: 0.238 (0.792)				
Ramsey RESET Test: 1.609 (0.133); Heteroskedasticity Test: 1.784 (0.179)				

Source: Author's estimate.

As shown by the positive correlation of 1.432740, the incidence of communicable diseases (CD) is correlated with the incidence of mortality rates (IMR). This further demonstrates infectious illnesses' role in contributing to infant mortality in Pakistan. Reducing the IMR and improving population health depends on successful efforts to fight and manage communicable illnesses. This research demonstrates the devastating effects of infectious illnesses on newborn health and mortality. Infants are more susceptible to communicable illnesses because their immune systems are still growing. In certain circumstances, newborns may even die from these disorders (Noppert et al., 2023) because of the significant health consequences they cause. There are several reasons for the correlation between CD rates and IMR to be positive. First, delays in diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of communicable illnesses may result from a lack of access to healthcare services, especially in rural and disadvantaged regions. Greater CD rates and hence greater IMR might result from inadequate healthcare infrastructure, a lack of healthcare personnel, and difficulties implementing preventative treatments like immunizations. In addition, poverty, poor sanitation, and insufficient nutrition contribute to the spread and severity of infectious illnesses (Ahmad et al., 2023) [citation needed]. The higher CD incidence among babies has been linked to inadequate access to necessities such as clean water, sanitation, and hygiene. Infants with compromised immune systems are more likely to get infections and die (Sharma Waddington et al., 2023) due to inadequate nutrition, such as malnutrition and deficits in critical micronutrients. High CD rates and their effect on IMR need for an all-encompassing strategy. Improving healthcare access, especially for marginalized groups, requires bolstering existing healthcare infrastructure. Examples include expanding access to healthcare experts and boosting the distribution of immunization programs and other preventative healthcare measures. It is also important to address the underlying socioeconomic determinants of health, such as housing, sanitation, and nutrition, contributing to poor health outcomes. The burden of communicable illnesses may be reduced and, in turn, IMR lowered by investing in poverty reduction programs, expanding access to safe water and sanitation, and encouraging healthy eating habits. The results have major repercussions for public health programs in Pakistan. Comprehensive initiatives for the prevention and control of communicable illnesses, as well as the improvement of healthcare systems, should be prioritized. Pakistan may decrease its IMR and improve the health of its baby population by tackling the causes of the country's high CD rate.

There is a statistically insignificant negative coefficient of -0.159 for NCDs ($p = 0.524$). This indicates that NCD incidence in Pakistan has no appreciable effect on IMR. However, non-communicable diseases (NCDs) may have far-reaching effects on people's health; tackling them is still essential for enhancing general wellness. A significant negative correlation of -0.476238 for Physicians per Capita (PHY) indicates that a larger ratio of physicians to residents correlates with a lower IMR. Evidence like this shows just how important it is for Pakistan to have sufficient trained medical personnel to lower infant death rates. Several factors contribute to the

existence of this bond. One benefit of a larger medical workforce is better access to care, especially for babies in rural or underdeveloped locations (Xiong et al., 2023). Increasing the number of doctors in more locations may speed up patient treatment, reduce travel time, and better respond to medical crises (Humayun et al., 2023). Second, in the context of baby care, having a fair number of doctors may improve coordination and continuity of treatment. Infant mortality may be reduced with preventative care measures such as regular doctor visits, vaccines, and early diagnosis of health problems. Doctors may help parents raise healthier babies by advising them on neonatal care, nutrition, and illness prevention (Norton et al., 2023). Further, doctors play a crucial role in identifying and treating communicable infections, which may significantly influence a baby's health. Their ability to identify and treat infections, provide appropriate medications, and advise on preventive measures can contribute to a decline in IMR associated with communicable diseases. The negative coefficient for PHY underscores the importance of investing in healthcare workforce development, including increasing the number of physicians in the country. This requires strategic planning to ensure an adequate supply of physicians, distribution across different regions, and addressing the shortage of healthcare professionals in underserved areas. Efforts should focus on expanding medical education programs, providing incentives for physicians to work in rural and remote areas, and supporting ongoing professional development and training opportunities (Wiedermann, 2023).

The constant term (C) has a coefficient of 3.520232, indicating the baseline IMR when all independent variables are zero. The R-squared value of 0.767748 suggests that the regression model explains approximately 76.77% of the variation in the IMR. This indicates that the selected independent variables collectively have a substantial impact on IMR in Pakistan. In conclusion, the findings indicate that the distribution and efficiency of CHE, the prevalence of CD, and the availability of PHY play crucial roles in shaping infant mortality outcomes in Pakistan. At the same time, education and environmental factors (represented by GEE and CO2) have little impact. These results highlight the need for specific policies and measures to improve healthcare access, tackle communicable illnesses, and strengthen the healthcare staff in Pakistan in order to lower the IMR and improve health outcomes overall.

Figure 3 shows that the CUSUM and CUSUM of Squares are within the 5% confidence interval, suggesting the model is stable. This result strengthens the confidence in the model's estimations and indicates that its connections among its variables are stable during the time under consideration.

Figure 3: CUSUM and CUSUM of Squares Test Estimates

Source: Author's extract.

Pakistan's economy has substantial policy and decision-making implications for verifying model stability. The model's estimations are reliable enough for policymakers to shape programs and strategies to reduce newborn and child mortality. Furthermore, the stable model might be a helpful instrument for tracking and gauging the efficacy of health intervention programs over time.

5. Conclusions

In order to effectively address health inequalities and promote equitable health outcomes, a thorough understanding of the interconnected nature of political institutions, power structures, and public health is required. In order to reduce death rates for children under five in Pakistan, this research concludes that political stability, effective policies for the social sector, and government initiatives are necessary. It stresses the need for healthcare workers to be involved in policymaking at all levels. It also necessitates an analytical review of other elements impacting healthcare costs. Several measures are needed to reduce the number of preventable deaths of infants and children in Pakistan. Since studies have revealed a link between women's education levels and child mortality rates, disseminating awareness and education among women is one successful strategy. Women's health and their children's health may benefit greatly from increased educational opportunities. Investing heavily in healthcare, particularly in underserved regions, means hiring more doctors, upgrading hospitals, and stocking emergency rooms with medications. This will aid in fixing the problems of insufficient healthcare, poor sanitation, and hygiene contributing to child mortality. Women who cannot make frequent trips to the hospital might have easier access to healthcare services by encouraging telemedicine. Medical advice and treatment may be delivered promptly via remote consultations and guidance made possible by technological advancements. Incentives like reduced total expenses for parents on their next visit to a pediatrician might be used by hospitals to promote immunization and routine exams for babies and newborns. This would improve baby healthcare monitoring in addition to raising immunization rates. Medical professionals have a unique opportunity to educate their own families about the value of vaccinations. Since people are more inclined to take a physician's advice than any other non-relative, this has the potential to increase vaccination rates greatly. Finally, private schools may help lower child death rates by requiring proof of vaccination before admitting pupils. This would ensure the safety of all children attending the school and preserve the health of the enrolled youngsters. The need for immunization should be further emphasized by warning parents of children who have not been immunized. In conclusion, reducing the high rate of infant and child mortality in Pakistan calls for a multifaceted strategy that includes increasing public knowledge and understanding, funding and expanding healthcare facilities and personnel, enhancing healthcare access through technology, and enacting policies and incentives to encourage preventative measures like vaccination and checkups. Taking these measures will have a major impact on improving the health of Pakistan's youth and lowering the country's child mortality rate. Transparency, accountability, and participatory decision-making are crucial as we manage the complexity of power, politics, and public health. Promoting health equality and participating in political processes may help us get closer to a world where power dynamics are used for good.

Ethical approval

Not Applicable.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

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Data and materials availability

The data is freely available at World Development Indicators published by World Bank (2023) at <https://databank.worldbank.org/source/world-development-indicators>.

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